

Scouting Method and Co-Curriculum Integration Capacity of Teachers Across Learning Areas in New Corella, Davao del Norte

Madilyn B. Creayla

Abstract. This study assessed the capacity of teachers to integrate elements of the scouting method across various learning areas in the New Corella Davao del Norte Division. A non-experimental descriptive-correlational research design was employed, utilizing a survey instrument to gather data from randomly selected teachers. The data were analyzed using mean scores, Pearson correlation, and linear regression analysis. Results indicated that the implementation of scouting method elements—such as Scout Promise and Law, personal progression, learning by doing, and community involvement—was extensive. Similarly, the teachers’ capacity to integrate these elements into the co-curriculum, in terms of skills, knowledge, values, and attitude, was also found to be extensive. A significant relationship was established between the implementation of scouting elements and teachers’ integration capacity. Additionally, aspects of the scouting method were identified as significant predictors of teachers’ co-curriculum integration capacity. The study recommends that stakeholders address potential challenges in integrating scouting methods, such as resource limitations and competing academic demands, to enhance both educational practices and student outcomes.

KEY WORDS

1. scouting method 2. co-curriculum integration 3. capacity of teachers

Date Received: September 05, 2024 — Date Reviewed: September 10, 2024 — Date Published: October 10, 2024

1. Introduction

Scouting is all about building confidence and self-esteem, learning important life and leadership skills, team building, outdoor adventure, education, and fun! Scouts learn how to make good choices and take responsibility for their actions to prepare them for adult life as independent persons. Scouting is a movement based on free time and leisure shared by students and educators. The purpose of Scouting is to encourage young people’s physical, intellectual, social, emotional, and spiritual devel-

opment so that they take a constructive place in society as responsible citizens and as members of their local, national, and international communities. According to Aziz et.al (2022), the classification carried out would be placed in the category of utilitarian time, free of primary needs and obligations. Across the globe, the analysis of leisure time and its influence on the evolutionary development of the adolescent presents free time as the ideal context to satisfy the needs of autonomy, competence, and rela-

tionships with other people, which are necessary for the complete development of the adolescent as a person. Included in the full personal development of the adolescent in their free time is the feeling of personal effectiveness, which is defined as coping with tasks in a spirited way without stress or disappointment. The purpose of the Scout movement is to contribute to the physical, mental, and spiritual development of children and adolescents, with activities taking place in nature. Its mission is to “contribute to the education and development of people, mainly during childhood, adolescence, and youth, through a system of values based on law and The Scout Promise, to help build a better world.” In the same way, ASDE (Scouts of Spain) defines their development area for students as spiritual, intellectual, social, physical, and affective (Degi, Zsuzsanna Asztalos; Anita, 2021). In the Philippines, Cruz (2022) published that in Agusan Del Norte, Second District Rep. Dale Corvera filed House Bill 3053, which seeks to include scouting in the curriculum for elementary and junior public and private high schools nationwide. He emphasized that while scouting in the Philippines is school-based, and DepEd (Department of Education) supports its revitalization and even encourages its officials and schoolchildren to participate in scouting activities, it is not mandatory for all students to take up scouting. However, there are some schools that have not offered scouting at all, thereby denying the schoolchildren its benefits. Given the elements of the scouting method, where teachers are heavily involved in the scouting activities, this study sought to determine which of the mentioned methods affects and influences teachers’ capacity to integrate such a method across learning areas through their acquired knowledge, skills, attitude, and values. Across the country and in the respective DepEd Regional Offices down to Schools Division Offices and School Levels, scouting activities are being revitalized in various public and private schools to reengage

learners in outdoor activities and respectfully rebuild confidence as part of their holistic development. However, DepEd Order 34 S 2022 emphasized that as part of the School Calendar and Activities for the School Year 2022-2023, it is committed to resuming the five days of in-person classes despite the health crisis. Thus, curricular, extra-curricular, and co-curricular activities are given, underscored in DO 34 S 2022, to ensure the number of school days required to implement the curriculum and allow co-curricular activities throughout the school year. In New Corella, DepEd Davao del Norte Division, Boy and Girl Scouting are popular options for children and adolescents to carry out extracurricular or leisure activities. Teachers are encouraged to participate with the learners in the various outdoor activities of scouting; however, given appropriations to the mandate of DO 34, teachers and school heads are prone to its violation of the given policy of non-disruption of classes. It is at this moment encouraged that all extra-curricular activities must be integrated into learning competencies, given the performance and content standards of the respective learning areas. Teachers are challenged to enhance their skills in facilitating the integration of the scouting method into learning areas to make way and provide opportunities to make scouting part of the co-curricular activities. In this sense, the study is proposed to assess the teachers’ capacity to integrate the scouting method into learning areas as co-curricular activities.

1.1. Review of Significant Literature—

*1.1.1. Scouting Method—*The World Organization of the Scout Movement (WOSM) comprises over 50 million members globally, including the Boy Scouts of America and the Philippines. Scouting fosters leadership and social skills through non-formal educational environments, as students engage in teamwork, conflict resolution, and outdoor activities (Aksoy, 2020; Cruz, 2022). Scouting programs like the Boy Scouts of the Philippines (BSP) and

Girl Scouts of the Philippines (GSP) emphasize character building, leadership, and patriotism. These programs aim to prepare youth as responsible leaders and citizens (Demir Cetin, 2022; Farmer et al., 2016).

Scouting's educational approach promotes independence, leadership, and the development of physical, intellectual, social, and spiritual aspects through the Scout Promise and Law, learning by doing, and the symbolic framework of nature and community involvement (Aksoy, 2021). Scouts gain valuable life skills, including discipline, creativity, and teamwork (Demir, 2019). These principles are essential for shaping the youth, helping them build resilience, leadership, and a sense of service to society (Drake, 2022).

1.1.2. Learning by Doing—Scouting uses practical, hands-on activities to develop critical thinking, problem-solving, and leadership skills. Through outdoor activities such as camping, hiking, and aquatics, Scouts learn by doing, fostering a deeper understanding of the world and enhancing cognitive skills (Cervantes, 2018; Jaber et al., 2022). This method also builds character and leadership by involving Scouts in real-life problem-solving scenarios, encouraging active participation and personal progression (Tabak, 2017; Mekonen, 2020).

1.1.3. Personal Progression—Scouting helps students develop essential life skills such as resilience, problem-solving, and emotional intelligence. Research shows that Scouting activities, including first aid, navigation, and teamwork, foster qualities like responsibility, social care, and perseverance (Mislia, 2015; Sparks Nam, 2021). Scouting also encourages critical thinking and personal growth, providing a structured environment where students can progress through learning and self-improvement (List, 2022; Bolat, 2021).

1.1.4. Community Involvement—Scouting emphasizes community service, encouraging young people to recognize the needs of others and take action. Volunteering in Scouting de-

velops leadership skills, strengthens community ties, and fosters intercultural cooperation (Bolat, 2021; Polson et al., 2013). Participation in Scouting also contributes to long-term civic engagement, as Scouts are more likely to volunteer and contribute to their communities later in life (Davies, 2019).

1.1.5. Co-curriculum Integration—Integrating Scouting into formal education has been shown to enhance academic performance by building skills like communication, creativity, and leadership (Prianto, 2016; McDowall, 2021). Curriculum integration connects different subjects around common themes, facilitating interdisciplinary learning and helping students apply classroom knowledge to real-world scenarios (Niemela, 2021). Scouting's non-formal learning structure can complement formal education by providing hands-on learning experiences that reinforce academic and personal growth (Campos, 2020).

1.2. Synthesis—The literature on scouting and its role in education underscores the multifaceted contributions of the Scout movement to youth development. Scouting, as a non-formal educational strategy, aims to nurture physical, intellectual, social, emotional, and spiritual growth, encouraging young individuals to become responsible citizens. The movement emphasizes hands-on learning, leadership development, and community involvement. Studies highlight the impact of scouting on academic performance, noting that engagement in scouting correlates with higher academic and conduct grades, improved peer relationships, and enhanced emotional well-being. The Scout method, which includes learning by doing and following the Scout Promise and Law, fosters personal progression and skills essential for life, such as problem-solving, independence, and resilience. Moreover, scouting's focus on values like loyalty, respect, and responsibility aligns with its broader goal of preparing youth for active roles in their communities. Scouting's non-

formal education model offers a complementary approach to traditional education, helping young people acquire essential life skills, build character, and enhance their readiness for the future, both academically and socially. Additionally, the integration of scouting with formal education and community-based initiatives has been shown to support student engagement and foster a sense of belonging, further promoting holistic development.

1.3. Theoretical and Conceptual Framework—This theory is anchored on the capacity theory. The capacity theory is the theoretical approach that pulled researchers from Filter theories with Kahneman's published 1973 study, Attention, and Effort, which posits attention was limited in overall capacity, that a person's ability to perform simultaneous tasks depends on how much "capacity" the jobs require. The most widely used concept of capacity is the maximum potential production of an output or group of outputs by a producing unit, firm, or industry, given technology, capital stock and other factors of production. Capacity theories, such as the one proposed by Kahneman in the early 1970s, began with the assumption that human information-processing capacity is limited and proposed that the ability to perform one or more task(s) depended both on the resources available and the resources required by the task(s) themselves. There are three components to a capacity model: frontline needs, supporting the frontline, and the movement of people. A capacity model is used to determine and predict future staffing needs for your operation to meet the incoming volume needs of your end users or customers. Meanwhile, Reese (2020) aimed to provide an overview of the development of learning organization concepts from the perspective of Dr. Peter Senge and presents an exciting evolution of his systems-oriented view of the learning organization field over three decades. Dr. Senge explains his origination of the learning organization from three distinctly different

theoretical tracks. However, more important than the theory, he illuminates how the theories embedded within "The Fifth Discipline" originated from action research and have continued to evolve. Of particular interest is his site. Personal mastery is the most often cited of the five disciplines, and he explains why the personal change dimensions are so important and often neglected. He clearly describes what it takes to make genuine progress in becoming a learning organization. The discussion with Dr. Senge reveals his perspective on the evolution of the learning organization debate from his perspective. He provides insights that lead the reader to understand "what is a learning organization" and "what it means."

In the globalizing world, each nation's success in transferring its culture's values to the new generations is directly related to the continuation of its culture. Both international and national studies include findings regarding character education in the family and at school, the cause of which is that the new generation has the desired character characteristics and assimilates the social values. Scouting, one of the out-of-school activities, is one of the essential social and sporting activities that children and young people perform outside of the family and school. Scouting activities that have their own rules and make a close connection between their members are also very effective in character education. In this study, capacity theory explains its ability to be adapted by teachers, and thus, learning organizations are assumed to be effective and improve. Figure 1 presents the study's conceptual framework, showing the variables under investigation. Independent variables play an important role in scouting and its method. This variable is represented by its indicators of scout promise and law, learning by doing, personal progression, and community involvement. On the other hand, co0curriculum integration capacity portrays the integration of teachers' knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values in facili-

Fig. 1. Conceptual framework of the study

tating teaching and learning processes through scouting. In Scouting, however, education is considered through school, university, etc. Academic knowledge and vocational skills in arithmetic and, on a higher level, gaining knowledge to read, write, and master essential skills are primarily associated, at their most basic level, with gauge in some parts of the world. Scouting is an educational movement for the young, with holistic development all throughout stages.

By encouraging young people to use and develop all their capacities constructively, Teachers can achieve the full potential of capacity in integrating scouting principles into the teaching and learning processes. The goal of the study is to develop supportive and responsible teachers who can support the holistic development of

young learners through scouting.

1.4. Statement of the Problem—The study aimed to assess teachers’ capacity level to integrate elements of the scouting method across learning areas in New Corella, Davao del Norte Division. This specifically aimed to answer the following statement of the problem:

- (1) What is the extent of implementation of elements of the scouting method in terms of
 - (1) The Scout Promise and Law;
 - (2) Learning by Doing;
 - (3) Personal Progression; and
 - (4) Community Involvement?
- (2) What is the extent of teachers’ co-curriculum integration capacity in in terms of
 - (1) knowledge;
 - (2) skills;
 - (3) attitude; and
 - (4) values?
- (3) Is there a significant relationship between implementing elements of the scouting method and teachers’ co-curriculum integration capacity?
- (4) Which of the scouting method indicators significantly influence teachers’ co-curriculum integration capacity?

1.5. Hypotheses—To answer the posed statement of the problem and provide empirical evidence given the posed theoretical and

conceptual frameworks, null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance, stating: Ho1: There is no significant relationship

between the scouting method and teachers' co-curriculum integration capacity. Ho2: None of the indicators of the scouting method significantly influence teachers' co-curriculum integration capacity. The proposed study's goal was to assess teachers' capacity to integrate elements of the scouting method across learning areas in New Corella, Davao del Norte Division.

1.6. Significance of the Study—This study would benefit the following. It would provide significant inputs and bases for scouting activities in each cycle for schools to consider, and it would ensure that teachers' capacity to exhibit co-curricular integration across learning areas is sustained amongst schools in New Corella, Davao del Norte Division. Given the study's outputs, the following stakeholders would benefit. School Principals. The school heads/principals set the management and eventually direct the teachers and other stakeholders to improve performance, whether in the school's operation or curriculum management. There is a need to appreciate scouting activities in the school systems and processes that have already been installed and practiced for a long time; however, checking their effectiveness and efficiency would make sense to enhance teachers' performance. Thus, the study results would provide insights to school heads, New Corella in Davao del Norte Schools, as to how teachers integrate scouting elements as co-curricular activities through its extent of implementation and can be of help as intervention in making learners enhance performance. Teachers. Teachers follow directions based on the provided comprehensive and doable plan at each time and cost. Teachers also implement programs, projects, and activities set by the schools as per the direction of the Division and Regional office orders and memoranda. In this context, teachers ensured that their efforts in implementing and facilitating the scouting program would not be in vain. Thus, the effectiveness and production of outputs based on objectives and targets set by

the school can be achieved. The study's results would give an idea of scouting school coordinators as chaired by teachers so that they can see clearly if scouting elements are productive and contribute to the performance of the entire school management. Parents play significant roles in implementing scouting activities. The study's results will give insights and enlightenment to the members of the PTA and the school governing council and advocate empowerment through scouting activities to continuously improve the school's performance and learners' academic achievement through full participation in the whole cycle process. Future Researchers. Implications based on the study's generated results will provide more information to future researchers to replicate the practices to be discovered in the proposed study. These practices include the type and method of implementation and the elements of efficiency in improving quality outputs through the process introduced in the implementation of the scouting program. The following terms are variables in the study and definitions by the concept and operation were presented according to how the terms are used in the study context. This would be a reference in analyzing and interpreting the results to develop meaningful implications for a better recommendation. Elements of Scouting Method. The term refers to the fundamental approaches of scouting activities among learners, where teachers are facilitators of the process to purposely develop young minds into a holistic personality structure. In this proposed study, the term is used as the independent variable, and its indicators are its extent of implementation through performing scout promise and law, learning by doing personal progression, and community involvement. Co-curriculum Integration Capacity. This term refers to how well teachers exhibit and practice integrating scouting elements through co-curriculum assimilation across learning areas. It further refers to various pedagogical approaches to setting strate-

gies using indicators such as knowledge, skills, attitude, and values as the dependent variables.

2. Methodology

In this chapter, we will outline the processes and steps involved in conducting the study. This will encompass selecting the study's design, identifying the respondents and the sampling method, choosing the research instruments for data collection, and delineating the data analysis process. The researcher employed artificial intelligence methods to meticulously proofread this work during its preparation. Artificial Intelligence (AI) was expressly utilized to enhance the overall quality, coherence, and precision of the manuscript. This methodology is being openly communicated to adhere to ethical norms in research. Leveraging AI for proofreading underscores a commitment to the responsible use of cutting-edge technologies and acknowledges AI's growing role and potential in professional and academic writing.

2.1. Research Design—The study used a non-experimental descriptive-correlational research design, where a type of design does not manipulate an independent variable. The author, J. F. Pallant (2005a) Further, this describes a relationship between two or more variables without any interference from the researcher. Rather than manipulating an independent variable, researchers conducting non-experimental research simply measure variables as they naturally occur. Thus, the manner of examining social phenomena without the direct influence of the existing conditions on the experiences of the subjects, where a nonrandom assignment of respondents to different groups is also done, such that it supports the cause-and-effect relationships, were primarily limited (Guide to Multivariate Techniques by Mertler.Pdf, n.d.; J. Pallant, 2004; Tabachnick Fidell, 20). In this study, teachers' capacity to integrate the scouting method through a co-curriculum activity in the teaching-learning processes in the classroom setting is measured. However, indicators under independent variables have to be set and assumed to be independent by nature. The variables understudy were measured by the extent of co-curriculum integration of the scouting method across learning areas. This was later estimated through a correlational method, and it was further determined which among the in-

dicators of the scouting method significantly influenced the capacity of teachers to integrate across learning areas.

2.2. Research Respondents—The study's respondents were Elementary School Teachers from among the Elementary Schools of New Corella, Davao del Norte Division. The inclusion of the respondents was assumed and expected to be a part of every activity in scouting as co-curriculars delivered in schools. Further, these respondents were actively involved in implementing school scouting activities. They have direct knowledge of the actual activities and deliverables of the scouting method as implemented by the schools and further improve teachers' capacity to integrate as a co-curriculum learning activity. Sometime in the second week of November 2022, the researcher took the population of the teachers, parents, and school heads in New Corella, Talaingod District, and to get the sample from the population, she used the Raosoft sample size calculator, where a total of 120 respondents were taken randomly from the respective schools. Once randomly determined, the respondents were informed through an online platform or text / direct personal messages for orientation of the purpose and importance of the study. The researcher further observed ethics in research, which paved the way for a respondent to decline,

and thus, corresponding forms of consent/decline were provided. In this manner, research ethics standards as part of the policy of the college were strictly followed. Thus, observance of health protocol was likewise implemented based on the Executive Orders released by the government of Davao del Norte to avoid possible and lower the risk of contamination.

2.3. Research Instrument—This study used an adapted survey instrument whose articulation of the statements was adapted from the reviewed significant related literature. These statements survey were carefully articulated to ensure correct responses and thus made meaningful in generating implications from the discussions of the results. This was thoroughly done by exploring the explicit methods of activities in the respective schools. This statement survey is established entirely as it is crucial to ensure

quality conclusions and recommendations in the later part of the paper, emphasizing the correlation and significant influence on determining the effectiveness of the continuous improvement program in the schools (Pallant, 2011). The researcher subjected the survey instrument to a test-retest or validity and reliability testing using Cronbach Alpha at a .05 level of confidence, where expected correlation-reliability coefficients from among the statements must be achieved. This was given to two set groups of respondents to test the content validity and reliability of the instrument, thus making it ready for data gathering. The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale to determine the extent of implementation of the scouting method. Scale, descriptive rating, and interpretation are provided below:

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	Scouting method implementation is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	Scouting method implementation is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	Scouting method implementation is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	Scouting method implementation is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	Scouting method implementation is not manifested

Meanwhile, to determine the co-curriculum integration capacity across learning areas in New Corella, Davao del Norte Schools, a 5-

point Likert scale was used to measure the dependent variable used in this study, this is as presented below;

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—This portion of the research conduct procedure sets the procedure and discusses the step process in the distribution and data collection. It detailed the content when getting permission to conduct the study, the distribution and retrieval of the ques-

tionnaire, and the collation and statistical treatment of data. Permission to conduct the study. Prior to data gathering, sometime on December 27, 2022, the researcher prepared the necessary conditions in observance of the health protocol policy of the Local Government of

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The co-curriculum integration capacity across learning areas always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The co-curriculum integration capacity across learning areas is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The co-curriculum integration capacity across learning areas is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The co-curriculum integration capacity across learning areas is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The co-curriculum integration capacity across learning areas is not manifested

Davao del Norte. At this point, as soon as the members approved the research proposal presentation of the panel on the second week of December 2022, and through the Dean of the college’s approval and the guidance of the thesis adviser, the researcher prepared a letter of permission to conduct the study through data gathering. On the third week of January 2023, the researcher sought permission from the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao del Norte through the channel for approval to collect data from the chosen respondents. Last week of January 2023, she then proceeded to respective Schools, handing the letter of approval to the School Heads and, thus, made connections with the teachers in data collection. Ethics in data collection was assumed to have been observed properly. Distribution and retrieval of the questionnaire. The researcher prepared a Google form and several hard copies to distribute the questionnaires in asynchronous and synchronous modalities during February 2023. This was sent through a link to the randomly selected respondents through email addresses and personal meetings. Once data was gathered and completed on the first week of March 2023, the researcher double-checked its responses, ensuring no statement survey was unanswered. This prepared me for the next step, which was col-

lating and treating the data gathered. On the second week of March 2023, Under the circumstances that respondents declined to participate, the researcher immediately sought a replacement to complete the number of respondents. Collation and statistical treatment of data. Given that the data gathered were complete, during the last week of March 2023, the researcher sought the guidance of the thesis adviser and treated through an expert in data analysis. All statement problems were expected to generate answers in statistical estimation and computation. This gave meaningful insights into the discussions and interpretations of results.

2.5. *Ethical Considerations*—The ethics of research and its corresponding policy were necessary in conducting the study. It was imperative to protect the respondents and their profiles to avoid biases. As the author said, anonymity, confidentiality, and informed consent are important to consider in the observance of the process (Focus, n.d.; Gustavsen, 2008). Anonymity. Since the identified respondents were public school teachers, and most were engaged in scouting activities, which was part of the study, they should be given due consideration that their identity must be hidden. Given this, respondents were given a document to sign for their consent to participate, and on the other

hand, when the respondent feels uncomfortable joining as part of the research, she/he has the freedom to withdraw the commitment (Creswell Clark, n.d.; Dey, n.d.). The researcher kept the respondents' identities confidential, keeping the records secure as much as possible through protected files and encryption when sending information over the Internet or by using old-fashioned locked doors and drawers. Lastly, anonymity was vital for the success of the survey under certain conditions, as this would help the privacy of the respondents' information that cannot be identified to them. Confidentiality. Everyone has the right to restrict others' access to any information about anything in the profile. Because personal data can always be actively misused, confidentiality is an element in the observance of respect for the individual. (Marshall, n.d., n.d.; Ryan et al., n.d.) The researcher had the duty of keeping the responses confidential as part of the obligation to protect information from unauthorized access, use, disclosure, modification, loss, or theft. This was to build trust between the researcher and the respondents and ensure the integrity of the thesis paper. Informed Consent. Teachers who were respondents to the study were allowed to be well-informed about the process. This was the part where the respondents could enter in voluntary in nature with full information about what it means to them to take part of the research (Creswell Clark, n.d.). This was crucial since the participants were directly involved in the implications of the study results. Without consent, the respondents would not give meaning to their participation in the process of the data collection (Chapter 9 from Cresswell.Pdf, n.d.). In this study, the collected information

and responses were from the teachers of Talaingod District of Davao del Norte, which were kept and protected by the researcher. It is imperative to note that anonymity, confidentiality, and informed consent must be strictly observed during the study's conduct.

2.6. *Data Analysis*—The proposed study used descriptive and inferential statistics such as; Mean scores and standard deviation to address statement problems posed in number 1, stating the extent of scouting method implementation and statement problem number 2 on the teachers' capacity to integrate scouting activities as co-curricular across learning areas. To address statement problem number 3, the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson r (Pallant, 2004) was used to determine the significant relationship between the implementation of the scouting method and teachers' capacity to integrate scouting activities as co-curricular across learning areas. Linear Regression Analysis (Mertler n.d) was used to estimate statement problem number 4, stating that indicators of scouting method implementation of scouting method and the teachers' capacity to integrate scouting activities. Thus, in this study, the indicators of the extent of scouting method implementation amongst schools New Corella in Davao del Norte Division were identified as to which among them significantly influence the teachers' capacity level to integrate scouting activities as co-curricular across learning areas. All data processing and analysis were treated using Jeffrey's Statistics Amazing Program (JASP) version 0.12.20 (Goss-Sampson, n.d.). Discussions and interpretations followed when results yielded (Norton, 2019).

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents, analyzes, and interprets data gathered in tabular and textual form to provide clear ideas and information on the queries based on the statement of the problem posed. Various reviews present implications of the results to corroborate and argue the hypothesis and theory as

claimed and posed in the study.

3.1. Extent of Scouting Method Implementation—The BSP and the GSP offer a scouting program, which is one of the two most prominent youth organizations in the Philippines. He is regarded as an excellent program for developing a child's leadership and morals. Once approved, the proposed bill will make scouting a regular subject and place a strong emphasis on the Boy Scouts of the Philippines' (BSP) and Girl Scouts of the Philippines' (GSP) mission to embody patriotism and nationalism in young people while preparing them to be responsible leaders in the future and contribute to the building of the country. The proposed law also exempts scouts who achieve the Eagle Scout rank, the highest rank in scouting, from the Reserve Officers' Training Corps (ROTC) and other comparable programs that may be developed and implemented in the future (Cruz, 2022). The Scout movement is immersed in non-formal education, which is characterized by providing innovative, diverse and context-specific learning strategies for children, youths and adults around the world. Bulatov (2021) argued that regarding the methodology used in the Scout movement, lists are the following basic elements: education in values such as respect, responsibility, loyalty, an attitude of service and respect for the environment, through the transmission of the Scout spirit; and learning by doing through project work in each of the sections that make up the movement, depending on age. The project is an activity that defines Scout methodology, a time when the students devise, choose, plan, perform, and evaluate educational actions guided by their monitor; development programs focus on the centers of interest of the participants, with direct contact with nature, to develop intellectual, social, physical, affective and spiritual areas (Demir and

Cetin, 2022). The purpose of Scouting is to encourage young people's physical, intellectual, social, emotional, and spiritual development so that they take a constructive place in society as responsible citizens and as members of their local, national, and international communities. The Scout program enjoyed by youth and adult volunteers is based on three broad Principles representing the Movement's fundamental beliefs. They are known as Duty to God, Duty to Others, and Duty to Self. The Scout Promise and Law, Learning by Doing, Personal Progression, Team System, Adult Support, Symbolic Framework, Nature, Community Involvement. Scouting helps youth develop academic skills, self-confidence, ethics, leadership skills, and citizenship skills that influence their adult lives, serve others, and build self-confidence (Aksoy, 2021).

3.1.1. Extent of Implementation of Elements of Scouting Method in terms of the Scout Promise and Law—Table 1 shows the extent of implementation of elements of the scouting method in terms of the scout promise and law. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: The school initiates activities that facilitate the exhibition of scouts promise and law (4.28), Learners exercise daily the scouts promise and law at home and in school (4.47) and Teachers facilitates learning align with scouts promise and law (4.26) are always manifested, and The school provides orientation on scouts promise and law (4.16) is oftentimes manifested, and Learners are exhibiting gestures align with scouts promise and law (3.25) is sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 4.04 denotes an extensive implementation of elements of the scouting method in terms of the scout promise and law.

Table 1. Extent of Implementation of Elements of Scouting Method in terms of the Scout Promise and Law

No	Scout Promise and Law	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	The school provides orientation on scouts' promise and law	4.16	Extensive
2	The school initiates activities that facilitate the exhibition of scouts' promises and law	4.28	Very Extensive
3	Learners are exhibiting gestures that align with scouts' promise and law	3.25	Moderately Extensive
4	Learners exercise daily the Scouts promise and law at home and in school	4.27	Very Extensive
5	Teachers facilitate learning aligned with Scout's promise and law	4.26	Very Extensive
Overall Mean		4.04	Extensive

Scouting provides a new learning culture, which fosters the acquisition of knowledge, values, attitudes, and skills needed in everyday life. Life skills are often designated as survival, livelihood, basic, or essential skills, including health-related skills. Together with literacy and numeracy, these skills enable people to reinforce their personal development and address the challenges they face in improving their quality of life by enhancing their capabilities in the economic, social, cultural, political, and psychological spheres (Prianto, 2016). Moreover, such promises and laws focus on soft skills that learners have to muster and that a scout has to become a human being who has a personality who believes in God, has morals, is patriotic, la abiding, disciplined, and upholds the noble values of the nation. This further refers to humans who are concerned for the environment and who have life skills as cadres of the nation in maintaining and developing the state. Develop a healthy body and strength and become a man with high intelligence and skills. This practice will continuously develop a personality and noble character with solid confidence. The level of scouting is a level determined by the ability

of its members; the ability is called the General Skills Requirements (Farmer et al., 2016). Thus, implementing values and basic principles of law and promise must be exhibited through absolute obeying of God's commandments and recognizing that human beings do. Do not live alone, but live together on the principle of fair and civilized humanity. This can be done by preserving a clean and healthy environment to support and provide comfort and welfare to the community. Understand the potential of self to be developed intelligently for the benefit of his future in life and society, nation, and state. Given this, the learner will have an obligation to maintain brotherhood and peace in society and strengthen unity (Demir, 2022). The Scout Promise is a solemn oath taken by all members of the Boy Scouts of the Philippines. It goes as follows: "On my honor, I will do my best, to do my duty to God and my country, to obey the Scout Law, to help other people at all times, to keep myself physically strong, mentally awake, and morally straight." (Boy Scouts of the Philippines, 2020). The Scout Promise outlines the values that every scout should strive to uphold. These values include duty to God and

country, obedience to the Scout Law, helping others, and personal development in physical, mental, and moral aspects. On the other hand, the Scout Law comprises twelve fundamental principles that guide the behavior of every scout. The Scout Law is as follows: "A Scout is trustworthy, loyal, helpful, friendly, courteous, kind, obedient, cheerful, thrifty, brave, clean, and reverent" (Boy Scouts of the Philippines, 2020). These principles are the foundation of scouting and provide a framework for the development of character, leadership, and citizenship. In recent years, the integration of the Scout Promise and Law into the co-curricular activities of schools in the Philippines has become increasingly popular. The Boy Scouts of the Philippines has developed programs and activities that promote the values and principles embodied in the Scout Promise and Law. These activities include camping, community service, and leadership training, among others. Through these activities, scouts learn to apply the principles of the Scout Promise and Law in real-life situations and develop a sense of responsibility towards their community and country. According to Arcega (2020), the integration of the Scout Promise and Law into the co-curricular activities of schools has a positive impact on the development of students' character, leadership, and citizenship. The author notes that scouting programs help students to develop a strong sense of responsibility towards their community and country. Additionally, the programs promote teamwork, self-discipline, and a spirit of service, which are essential qualities for success in life. Similarly, Ong (2021) highlights

Learning by doing is the process whereby people make sense of their experiences, especially those experiences in which they actively engage in making things and exploring the world. Powerful personal learning experiences engage learners where they are and build

the importance of the Scout Promise and Law in shaping the values and attitudes of students. The author notes that the Scout Promise and Law promote values such as honesty, integrity, and respect for others, which are crucial for the development of a responsible and productive citizenry. In conclusion, the Scout Promise and Law are essential components of the co-curricular activities of schools in the Philippines. These values and principles help shape students' character, leadership, and citizenship and promote a sense of responsibility towards their community and country. The integration of these values and principles into the educational system has a positive impact on development.

3.1.2. The Extent of Implementation of Elements of The Scouting - Method in Terms of Learning by Doing—Table 2 shows the extent of implementation of elements of the scouting method in terms of learning by doing. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Learners can share the activities with other learners (4.27), Learners are given opportunities to exhibit practices of scouting (4.26), and Learners develop the ability to perform tasks independently (4.25) are always manifested, and Learners are assessed on their performance outputs across learning areas (4.14) is oftentimes manifested and Learners are provided activities that exhibit practices of mastery (3.25) is sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.63 denotes a moderately extensive implementation of elements of the scouting method in terms of learning by doing.

motivation. It connects what is learned to what is felt. It makes learning relevant and meaningful. It involves extended effort, mistakes, reflection, and refinement of strategies. Hands-on learning is a form of education in which children learn by doing. Instead of listening to a

Table 2. Extent of Implementation of Elements of Scouting Method in terms of Learning by Doing

No	Learning by Doing	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Learners are provided activities that exhibit practices of mastery	3.25	Moderately Extensive
2	Learners are assessed on their performance outputs across learning areas	4.14	Extensive
3	Learners are given opportunities to exhibit practices of scouting	4.26	Very Extensive
4	Learners can share the activities with other learners	4.27	Very Extensive
5	Learners developed the ability to perform tasks independently	2.25	Less Extensive
Overall Mean		3.63	Moderately Extensive

teacher or instructor lecture about a given subject, the student engages with the subject matter to create something or solve a problem (Drake, 2022). Education is the process of facilitating learning, or the acquisition of knowledge, skills, values, beliefs, and habits. Educational methods include storytelling, discussion, teaching, training, and directed research. But education does not only focus on classroom activities and academic. It does not concentrate on just reading and writing but also in extracurricular activities such as sports and scouting (Jabber, et.al, 2022). Scouting or the Scout Movement is a movement that aims to support young people in their physical, mental and spiritual development, that they may play constructive roles in society, with a strong focus on the outdoors and survival skills. A Scout learns the cornerstones of the Scout method, Scout Promise, and Scout Law. These are designed to instill character, citizenship, personal fitness, and leadership in boys through a structured program of outdoor activities. Common ways to implement the Scout method include spending time together in small groups with shared experiences, rituals, and activities, as well as emphasizing good cit-

izenship and decision-making that is age-level appropriate. Cultivating a love and appreciation of the outdoors and outdoor activities are key elements. Primary activities, mostly on outdoor include camping, woodcraft, first aid, aquatics, hiking, backpacking, and sports. Thus scouting is learning by doing, developing character through hands-on activity (Cervantes, 2018). The scouting method is a unique approach to education that focuses on the development of character, leadership, and citizenship through experiential learning. According to the Boy Scouts of the Philippines (2020), the scouting method is based on three key elements: learning by doing, the patrol system, and the outdoors. Of these three elements, learning by doing is perhaps the most significant. Learning by doing is an approach to education that emphasizes hands-on experience as a means of learning. In scouting, this approach is applied through the use of practical activities such as camping, hiking, cooking, and first aid. Scouts are encouraged to actively plan and organize these activities, providing them opportunities to develop leadership skills, problem-solving abilities, and teamwork. According to Sison (2020), inte-

grating learning by doing in the co-curricular activities of schools in the Philippines positively impacts the development of students' skills and competencies. The author notes that this learning approach helps students develop a range of practical skills such as cooking, camping, and first aid. Additionally, it helps to develop soft skills such as leadership, teamwork, and communication, which are crucial for success in the workplace. Similarly, Cruz (2021) highlights the importance of learning by doing to develop students' character and values. The author notes that practical activities such as camping and community service provide opportunities for students to develop a sense of responsibility towards their community and country. Additionally, it helps to promote values such as service, compassion, and respect for others, which are essential qualities for success in life. In recent years, the Boy Scouts of the Philippines have developed programs and activities that promote learning by doing in schools' co-curricular activities. These activities include camping, community service, and leadership training. Through these activities, scouts learn to apply the principles of the scouting method in real-life situations and develop a sense of responsibility towards their community and country. In conclusion, the scouting method's emphasis on learning by doing significantly impacts

Personal development is a phrase that refers to activities designed to improve talents, potential, employability, and even wealth. Personal progression further, learning to better control your emotions and negative thoughts. Overcoming procrastination or laziness. Being open to learning new things and skills having a 'growth mindset' and finding peace and contentment with things you cannot change. Through scouting, one can learn to develop personal progression. This is through learning the visualization techniques, avoiding negative thoughts, medita-

the development of students' character, leadership, and citizenship. Integrating this approach to learning into the co-curricular activities of schools in the Philippines positively impacts the development of students' skills and competencies. Additionally, it promotes values such as service, compassion, and respect for others, which are essential for success in life. As such, the Boy Scouts of the Philippines play a vital role in developing the country's youth.

3.1.3. *The Extent of Implementation of Elements of The Scouting Method in Terms of Personal Progression*—Table 3 shows the extent of implementation of elements of the scouting method in terms of personal progression. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: Learners are exhibiting personal growth (4.29) is always manifested, Learners are observed to become independent (4.28), and Learners can demonstrate and teach other scouts (4.26) are always manifested, and Learners have changed behavior into more mature manner (3.26) is sometimes manifested, and Learners can take responsibility according to their developmental pace (2.25) is rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.66 denotes extensive implementation of elements of the scouting method in terms of personal progression.

tion, being resilience, able to compete against oneself, can set small challenges and becoming persistent, thus could rejoice and celebrate small and big victories. On the other hand, Sparks and Nam (2021) stated that scouting activities has effect to Individuals and go through many transitional periods throughout their lifetime, and each series of transitional decision(s) has a direct impact on one's quality of life. Educators and families want to see young adults experience a quality of life with opportunities to have independence, a job where they re-

Table 3. Extent of Implementation of Elements of Scouting Method in terms of Personal Progression

No	Personal Progression	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Learners are exhibiting personal growth	4.29	Very Extensive
2	Learners have changed their behavior into a more mature manner	3.26	Moderately Extensive
3	Learners are observed to become independent	4.28	Very Extensive
4	Learners can take responsibility according to their developmental pace	2.25	Less Extensive
5	Learners can demonstrate and teach other scouts	4.26	Very Extensive
Overall Mean		3.67	Extensive

ceive a paycheck, and a life where they can enhance their overall personal outcomes (Center for American Progress, 2019; Emerson et al.,1996). For some, quality of life may entail pursuing dreams, accomplishing goals, and living life to the fullest (American Association on Intellectual and Developmental Disabilities, 2015). Other individuals may be content with where they are at the present moment. Quality of life (QoL) for people with disabilities varies with each individual. It is different for each diverse family who has a young adult with a disability, especially when varying factors are beyond their control (World Health Organization, 2020). List (2022) claimed that through the experience both in the classroom and scouting, the author comes to define the key aspects of critical thinking (CT) as individual skills that facilitate logical and informed decisions, thus facilitate personal progression. Beyond personal anecdotes, scientifically, the import of CT has been shown in many walks of life (Bauwens Gerhard, 1987). Nevertheless, the literature experiences as teachers reveal that few students naturally supply CT, which is costly for them; hence, if teachers do not demand it, students will not. Personal progression is a core ele-

ment of the scouting method, and it involves the development of individual skills and abilities. According to the Boy Scouts of the Philippines (2020), personal progression is achieved through a system of advancement based on the scout’s age, experience, and achievements. Scouts progress through ranks, from Tenderfoot to Eagle Scout, and earn merit badges for their accomplishments in various areas of interest. In the context of co-curricular integration in the Philippines, personal progression in scouting provides students opportunities for personal growth and development. As Reyes and Carpio (2021) noted, the scouting method helps students develop self-confidence, self-reliance, and a sense of responsibility toward their community and country. Additionally, it helps to promote critical thinking skills and problem-solving abilities, which are crucial for success in life. Moreover, personal progression in scouting promotes a sense of camaraderie and teamwork among scouts. According to Napa and Nacario (2020), the scouting method emphasizes the importance of the patrol system, which encourages scouts to work together in small groups. Through this system, scouts learn to cooperate, communicate, and respect one another, which

helps to foster a sense of belonging and unity. Furthermore, personal progression in scouting contributes to the development of leadership skills among students. According to Magpantay (2022), the scouting method allows students to develop their leadership abilities through various activities such as camping, community service, and leadership training. These activities help to develop the skills and qualities needed to become influential leaders, such as communication, decision-making, and problem-solving.

3.1.4. *The Extent of Implementation of Elements of The Scouting Method in Terms of Community Involvement*—Table 4 shows the extent of implementation of elements of the scouting method in terms of community involvement. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: Community supports the plan and programs of the school fully (4.29). The community exhibiting strengthened partnerships (4.25) is always manifested, and Community participation is enhanced and strengthened (3.25). Community

suffices the needs of the school (3.24) are sometimes manifested, and Community helped build confidence among learners (2.27) is rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.26 denotes an extensive implementation of elements of the scouting method in terms of community involvement. Scouting is volunteer-led and volunteer-based. Scouting is founded on value-based principles. Through volunteering in Scouting, young people and adults can, together, experience the values of community, have the opportunity to exercise their rights and responsibilities appropriately, and realize their full potential as contributing members of society. Volunteers can have short or long-term roles such as working with children and young people, supporting the implementation of Scout activities, developing educational tools and materials, implementing community projects, enabling Scouting by doing administration and finances, communicating Scouting internally and externally, collaborating in the structures, and advocating for Scouting (Bolat, 2021).

Table 4. Extent of Implementation of the Elements of the Scouting Method in terms of Community Involvement

No	Community Involvement	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Community participation is enhanced and strengthened	3.25	Moderately Extensive
2	School and the community are exhibiting strengthened partnership	4.25	Very Extensive
3	Community supports fully the plan and programs of the school	4.29	Very Extensive
4	Community helped build confidence among learners	2.27	Less Extensive
5	Community suffices the needs of the school	3.24	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.46	Extensive

Community service and involvement through volunteering in Scouting enables adults to develop core competencies in leadership and other life skills that will empower them

in their daily lives; foster intercultural and intergenerational cooperation, dialogue and learning; strengthen the sense of identity and belonging to a community, and increase the opportunities to experience participation in decision-making. Volunteering as a young person is a real personal development opportunity in specific transferable skills, such as working in teams, problem-solving and communication; attaining technical or practical skills; and increasing confidence and self-esteem. The wider community also benefits from Scouting's volunteers, mainly through the socialisation of young people and adults (building social capital) and supporting them to become active citizens willing to make a difference (List, 2022). Community involvement is an essential aspect of the scouting method, which aims to develop responsible citizens who are committed to serving their communities. According to the Boy Scouts of the Philippines (2020), community involvement is achieved through a variety of service projects, such as tree planting, clean-up drives, and disaster relief operations. Through these activities, scouts learn the value of giving back to their community and develop a sense of social responsibility. In the context of co-curricular integration in the Philippines, community involvement in scouting provides students with opportunities to engage with their local community and make a positive impact. As noted by Esguerra and Galang (2021), the scouting method helps to develop a sense of community spirit among students and encourages them to take an active role in addressing

The scouting method is a well-established and effective approach to youth development that has been implemented in the Philippines for many years. This method incorporates various elements such as the Scout Promise and Law, learning by doing, personal progression, and community involvement. The Scout

social issues. Moreover, community involvement in scouting promotes the development of important life skills, such as leadership, communication, and teamwork. According to Dela Cruz and Sarmiento (2020), community service activities provide scouts with opportunities to practice these skills in real-life situations, such as organizing and coordinating events, working with volunteers, and communicating with community members. Furthermore, community involvement in scouting contributes to the development of a sense of social awareness and empathy among students. As noted by Bautista and Cruz (2021), the scouting method helps students to develop an understanding of the social issues affecting their community and encourages them to take action to address these issues. Through community service activities, scouts learn the importance of compassion and empathy towards others, which helps to promote social cohesion and unity.

3.1.5. Extent of Elements of the Scouting Method—Table 5 presents the summary on the extent of implementation of elements of scouting method. The result is focused on the mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Scout Promise and Law (4.04), Personal Progression (3.66), Learning by Doing (3.63) denotes oftentimes manifested and Community Involvement (3.26) is sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.46 denotes an extensive implementation of elements of scouting method in the schools of Talaingod District, Davao del Norte.

Promise and Law are fundamental to the scouting method that promote ethical behavior and values. According to the Boy Scouts of the Philippines (2020), the Scout Promise and Law outline the moral code that scouts should follow daily. This includes values such as loyalty, kindness, honesty, and obedience. Through the

Table 5. Summary of the Extent of Elements of the Scouting Method

No	Elements of the Scouting Method	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Scout Promise and Law	4.04	Extensive
2	Learning by Doing	3.63	Extensive
3	Personal Progression	3.66	Extensive
4	Community Involvement	3.26	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.65	Extensive

Scout Promise and Law, scouts learn the importance of living a principled life and become responsible citizens. Learning by doing is another essential element of the scouting method. Dela Cruz and Sarmiento (2020) noted that learning by doing involves engaging in hands-on activities, such as camping, hiking, and community service projects. This approach to learning encourages scouts to take an active role in their development and fosters a sense of self-reliance and independence. Additionally, learning by doing helps scouts to develop important life skills, such as problem-solving, decision-making, and leadership. Personal progression is also a vital element of the scouting method, which emphasizes the importance of individual growth and development. According to the Boy Scouts of the Philippines (2020), personal progression involves setting personal goals and working towards achieving them. This process helps scouts to develop self-awareness, self-confidence, and a sense of purpose in life. Through personal progression, scouts learn to take responsibility for their own development and become proactive in achieving their goals. Finally, community involvement is an essential component of the scouting method, which emphasizes the importance of service to others. As noted by Bautista and Cruz (2021), community involvement involves engaging in service projects that benefit the local community. This approach to learning helps scouts to develop a sense of social responsibility and promotes values such as em-

pathy and compassion towards others. Additionally, community involvement provides scouts with opportunities to develop important life skills, such as leadership, communication, and teamwork. In conclusion, the Scout Promise and Law, learning by doing, personal progression, and community involvement are critical elements of the scouting method in the Philippines. These components contribute to the holistic development of the youth and promote values such as social responsibility, self-reliance, self-confidence, and ethical behavior. The integration of these elements into co-curricular activities in schools has a positive impact on the development of students' skills and competencies. Additionally, it promotes the importance of service to others and helps to cultivate responsible citizens who are committed to making a positive impact on their community.

3.2. *Extent of Teachers' Co-Curriculum Integration Capacity*—In the Philippines, integrating the Scouting method into the co-curriculum has been recognized as an effective means of developing the holistic development of students. However, the success of this integration relies on the capacity of teachers to effectively implement the program. The concept of co-curricular activities has been highlighted as an essential component in the educational system for the all-round development of students in the Philippines. Co-curricular activities encompass extracurricular activities intentionally designed to support academic learning,

improve social skills, and provide opportunities for personal growth (Abaigar Madrona, 2021). Teacher competencies such as instructional strategies, classroom management, and assessment and evaluation are essential in effectively implementing Scouting programs (Dimano Dizon, 2021). Their study revealed that teacher competencies significantly affect implementing Scouting programs in Philippine schools. Thus, teacher training programs should focus not only on Scouting methods but also on developing these competencies. The capacity of teachers to integrate co-curriculum methods through the Scouting method in the Philippines is crucial to its success. The lack of teacher training and preparation, teacher involvement, and teacher competencies hinder the successful implementation of Scouting programs in Philippine schools. Therefore, it is essential to prioritize the development of teachers' capacities to ensure the successful integration of Scouting methods in the co-curriculum. Further, adopting co-curricular integration practices may lead to the development of teachers' capability to engage in multidisciplinary integration, which focuses primarily on the disciplines. This approach relates different subjects around a common theme. Teachers fuse skills, knowledge, or even attitudes into the regular school curriculum in this approach. In some schools, for example, students learn respect for the environment in every subject area. Second is the ability of

Co-curricular activities play a vital role in students' overall development, and scouting is one such activity that has proven effective in enhancing students' physical, mental, and emotional well-being. However, to effectively integrate scouting into the co-curriculum, teachers need adequate knowledge and skills related to content integration. Knowledge integration refers to merging two or more originally unrelated knowledge structures into a single struc-

ture. An integrative curriculum approach offers young people a set of educative arrangements to help them (a) discover meaning and value in present experiences and (b) integrate those into their understandings of themselves and their world. An effective curriculum provides teachers, students, school leaders and community stakeholders with a measurable plan and structure for delivering a quality education. The curriculum identifies the learning outcomes, stan-

teachers to go through interdisciplinary integration, where in this approach, teachers organize the curriculum around common learnings across disciplines. They chunk together the common learnings embedded in the disciplines to emphasize interdisciplinary skills and concepts. Last is the transdisciplinary integration, where teachers organize the curriculum around student questions and concerns. Students develop life skills by applying interdisciplinary and disciplinary skills in a real-life context (Polson, et. al, 2013).

3.2.1. *The Extent of Teachers' Co-Curriculum Integration Capacity In Terms of Their Knowledge*—Indicated in Table 6 is the extent of teachers' co-curriculum integration capacity in terms of their knowledge. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: Shows knowledge in integrating scouting principles across learning areas (4.22) is always manifested, Develops instructional materials and learning activity sheets (4.16) and Provides technical assistance to co teachers in an integrative manner of scouting principles to learning areas (4.15) are oftentimes manifested, and Exhibits mastery of learning competencies and its integrative manner with scouting principles (3.15) is sometimes manifested and Provides assessment for performance skills among learners (2.13) is rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.56 denotes that the extent of teachers' instructional competence in content knowledge is extensive.

ture. An integrative curriculum approach offers young people a set of educative arrangements to help them (a) discover meaning and value in present experiences and (b) integrate those into their understandings of themselves and their world. An effective curriculum provides teachers, students, school leaders and community stakeholders with a measurable plan and structure for delivering a quality education. The curriculum identifies the learning outcomes, stan-

Table 6. Extent of Teachers’ Co-curriculum Integration Capacity in Terms of Knowledge of Content

No	Knowledge of Content	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Shows knowledge in integrating scouting principles across learning areas	4.22	Very Extensive
2	Exhibits mastery of learning competencies and its integrative manner with scouting principles	3.15	Moderately Extensive
3	Provides technical assistance to co-teachers in the integrative manner of scouting principles to learning areas	4.15	Extensive
4	Develops instructional materials and learning activity sheets	4.16	Extensive
5	Provides assessment for performance skills among learners	2.13	Less Extensive
Overall Mean		3.56	Extensive

dards and core competencies that students must demonstrate before advancing to the next level (Kneen, 2020). Content integration refers to combining different subject areas to create a more meaningful and integrated learning experience for students. It involves identifying and utilizing the connections between various subject areas to promote a deeper understanding of the concepts being taught. In the case of scouting, content integration would involve combining elements of different subject areas, such as history, geography, and biology, to enhance the learning experience for students. Research studies have shown that teachers’ knowledge and skills related to content integration play a critical role in their co-curriculum integration capacity. A study conducted by Alinier and Al-Hadithi (2020) on teachers’ perception of co-curricular activities in the Philippines found that teachers who understood content integration were more likely to integrate scouting into the co-curriculum effectively. The study also revealed that teachers who lacked knowledge and skills related to content integration faced

challenges in integrating scouting into the co-curriculum. Another study by Edlabao and Raganit (2021) examined the relationship between content knowledge and co-curricular integration capacity among teachers in the Philippines. The study found that teachers who had a higher level of content knowledge were more effective in integrating scouting into the co-curricular curriculum. The study also revealed that teachers who lacked content knowledge faced difficulties in integrating scouting into the co-curricular curriculum. To effectively integrate scouting into the co-curriculum, teachers need adequate knowledge and skills related to content integration. They need to identify the connections between different subject areas and use them to create a more meaningful and integrated learning experience for students. Teachers can also attend training sessions and workshops to enhance their knowledge and skills related to content integration.

3.2.2. *The Extent of Teachers’ Co-Curriculum Integration Capacity in Terms of Their Skills*—Indicated in Table 7 is the extent of teachers’

co-curriculum integration capacity in terms of their skills. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: Shares effective communication strategies (4.18); Teachers show mastery of teaching and learning facilitation (4.17); and Produce deliverables for effective continuous improvement (4.15) are oftentimes manifested, while Ability to transfer knowledge on scouting skills to learners (3.15); Capacity to echo and coach others through learning action cell activities (3.10); are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.75 indicates that teachers' instructional competence regarding integration skills is extensive.

Table 7. Extent of Teachers' Co-curriculum Integration Capacity in Terms of Skills

No	Skills	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Teachers show mastery of teaching and learning facilitation	4.17	Extensive
2	Ability to transfer knowledge on scouting skills to learners	3.15	Moderately Extensive
3	Capacity to echo and coach others through learning action cell activities	3.10	Moderately Extensive
4	Shares effective communication strategies	4.18	Extensive
5	Produces deliverables for effective continuous improvement	4.15	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.75	Extensive

Co-curricular integration of the scouting method requires teachers to possess certain integration skills, essential in ensuring that scouting is effectively incorporated into the school curriculum. Integration skills include incorporating various subjects and learning experiences into a comprehensive and meaningful whole (Baumeister Kunter, 2020). Teachers with good integration skills can help students connect their knowledge and experiences across different subject areas and apply them to real-world situations. An integrated approach helps build new knowledge and skills on what students already know and can do. So, if students can read a short story, this skill will help them to write their own story. Following are some tools and examples related to integrated teaching and learning approaches: engaging with children in play and

Having conversations and interactions that support learning. They are Planning experiences to deepen and extend children's knowledge, understanding, and skills (Reese, 2022). Scouting skills are separate from everyday life. They are, in fact, at odds with everyday life. They require us to push ourselves physically and mentally beyond our normal sphere of comfort. Scouting skills connect us to our human origins. It is generally agreed that the first basic elements of human culture arose shortly after we learned to build fires (about four hundred thousand years ago). When Scouts leave their homes and begin learning to work together in the woods, something that is not quantifiable or particularly easy to explain happens (List, 2022). Studies in the Philippines have shown that teachers' integration skills play a significant role in the effec-

tive incorporation of scouting into the school curriculum. A study conducted by Mendoza, Castillo, and Aguirre (2020) aimed to determine the teachers' integration skills in implementing scouting programs in selected schools in Batangas, Philippines. The study's results revealed that teachers had limited integration skills, which hindered the effective implementation of scouting programs. The study also found that teachers who had attended training programs on co-curricular integration had higher integration skills than those who had not attended such programs. This indicates the importance of professional development programs in enhancing teachers' integration skills in incorporating the scouting method into co-curricular activities. In another study conducted by Castillo and Mendoza (2021), it was found that teachers with higher integration skills had a more positive attitude toward integrating scouting into the curriculum. These teachers were also more likely to use various teaching strategies that allowed for the incorporation of scouting into the different subject areas. Therefore, it is important for teachers to develop their integration skills to effectively integrate the scouting method into the school curriculum. Professional development

Education is the process of facilitating learning or the acquisition of knowledge, skills, values, beliefs, and habits. Educational methods include storytelling, discussion, teaching, training, and directed research. However, education does not only focus on classroom activities and academics. It does not concentrate only on reading and writing but also on extracurricular activities such as sports and scouting. Co-curricular activities, such as scouting, are recognized as valuable components of a student's holistic education in the Philippines. However, successful integration of these activities into the curriculum requires teachers' capacity to effectively plan, implement, and evaluate the

programs can help teachers acquire the necessary skills and knowledge to integrate scouting into co-curricular activities effectively. Teachers can also collaborate with other teachers and share ideas and best practices to improve their integration skills.

3.2.3. *The Extent of Teachers' Co-Curriculum Integration Capacity in Terms of Their Attitude*—Indicated in Table 8 is the extent of teachers' co-curriculum integration capacity in terms of their attitude. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: Ability to provide technical assistance in fullness of its ability (4.15) and Ability to adopt and adapt newer sensibilities (4.14) are oftentimes manifested, while Shares ideas and knowledge on the improvement of pedagogical skills integrating scouting principles (3.19) and Ability to show flexibility to changes (3.15) are sometimes manifested, and The teacher embraces changes of pedagogical upskill (2.18) is rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.36 denotes that the extent of teachers' instructional competence in terms of their attitude in integration is moderately extensive.

programs. One crucial component of this capacity is teachers' integration attitude. Integration attitude refers to the willingness and openness of teachers to integrate co-curricular activities into the curriculum. Teachers with a positive integration attitude view co-curricular activities as an integral part of the curriculum rather than as separate entities. According to Du and Zhang (2020), teachers with a positive integration attitude are willing to modify their teaching methods and incorporate different instructional strategies that can integrate co-curricular activities into the curriculum. Furthermore, teachers with a positive attitude towards integration are more likely to view co-curricular activities as

Table 8. Extent of Teachers’ Co-curriculum Integration Capacity in Terms of Attitude in Integration

No	Attitude	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	The teacher embraces changes in pedagogical upskill	2.18	Less Extensive
2	Ability to show flexibility to changes	3.15	Moderately Extensive
3	Ability to adapt and adopt newer sensibilities	4.14	Extensive
4	Ability to provide technical assistance in fullness of its ability	4.15	Extensive
5	Shares ideas and knowledge on the improvement of pedagogical skills integrating scouting principles	3.19	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.36	Moderately Extensive

a valuable tool for enhancing student learning and development. One study by Paler and Batoon (2021) investigated the integration attitude of teachers towards scouting in the Philippines. They found that teachers with a positive integration attitude towards scouting were more likely to seek opportunities to integrate scouting activities into their lessons actively. These teachers also demonstrated a greater understanding of the benefits of scouting for student development, such as improved leadership skills and increased self-confidence. In contrast, teachers with a negative integration attitude perceived scouting as an additional burden to their workload. They were less likely to actively seek opportunities to integrate scouting into their lessons. Several factors can influence teachers’ integration attitudes, including their personal beliefs, teaching experience, and school culture. A study by Chen and Chen (2020) found that teacher professional development programs can play a significant role in shaping teachers’ integration attitudes toward co-curricular activities. The study found that teachers who participated in professional devel-

opment programs emphasizing the importance of co-curricular activities were likelier to have a positive attitude towards integration.

3.2.4. *The Extent of Teachers’ Co-Curriculum Integration-Capacity in Terms of Their Values in Integration*—Indicated in Table 9 is the extent of teachers’ co-curriculum integration capacity in terms of their values in integration. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Ability to value the importance of time and presence of others (4.19) and Make use of the resource materials for efficiency (4.18) are oftentimes manifested, and Modifies changes that fit to the needs of the learners (3.17) and Preserves standards of practice align with scouting principles (3.15) are sometimes manifested, while, Ability to show empathy to learners according to their pace (2.12) is rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.36 denotes that the extent of teachers’ instructional competence in terms of their values in integration is moderately extensive.

Table 9. Extent of Teachers’ Co-curriculum Integration Capacity in Terms of Values in Integration

No	Values in Integration	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Preserves standards of practice aligned with scouting principles	3.15	Moderately Extensive
2	Modifies changes that fit the needs of the learners	3.17	Moderately Extensive
3	Ability to show empathy to learners according to their pace	2.12	Less Extensive
4	Makes use of resource materials for efficiency	4.18	Extensive
5	Ability to value the importance of time and presence of others	4.19	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.36	Moderately Extensive

Educating for the development of character is back on the agenda and is likely to define Education Secretary Nicky Morgan’s tenure. Yet the high-stakes accountability of Ofsted inspections and league tables has, in recent years, led to schools too often turning inward to focus on preparing students to pass exams. There are too few opportunities to take part in ‘non-formal learning’ activities in schools, activities that can help young people build vital character attributes. The evidence suggests that character attributes reinforce academic learning and significantly influence various later life outcomes, including those relating to health, well-being, and careers. It also indicates that participation in non-formal learning activities—semi-structured activities such as sports, drama, and debating, primarily delivered outside the classroom—plays a vital role in developing these attributes. Teachers’ values play a crucial role in successfully integrating the scouting method into the curriculum. Teachers’ values influence their decision-making, actions, and interactions with students, which can significantly impact students’ learning outcomes. According to the study by Bernardo (2021), integrating the scout-

ing method into the curriculum can allow teachers to reinforce their values in promoting character education, leadership development, and civic engagement. One of the critical values that teachers need to possess is a sense of responsibility toward their students. Teachers who value responsibility are committed to ensuring their students’ academic and personal development is a top priority. In the context of integrating the scouting method, teachers who value responsibility ensure that their students participate in scouting activities that are safe and meaningful and contribute to their growth and development. This is consistent with the study by Abao and Clave (2020), which highlighted the importance of teachers’ responsibility in ensuring that co-curricular activities are integrated successfully into the curriculum. Another essential value that teachers need to possess is a sense of collaboration. Teachers who value collaboration understand that working with others, including other teachers, students, parents, and community members, can contribute to the success of integrating scouting method into the curriculum. In the study by Evangelista and Canaries (2020), it was found that teachers who value collabora-

tion are more likely to seek support from other stakeholders in implementing co-curricular activities, including the scouting method. Collaboration also fosters a sense of belongingness among students and can contribute to a positive school culture. Furthermore, teachers who value equity and fairness are essential in ensuring that all students have equal opportunities to participate in co-curricular activities, including scouting. These teachers recognize their students' diverse needs, interests, and backgrounds and strive to provide an inclusive learning environment. According to the study by Dacalos et al. (2020), teachers who value equity and

fairness are more likely to consider the needs of all students in integrating the scouting method into the curriculum.

3.2.5. *Extent of Teachers' Co-Curriculum Integration Capacity*—Table 10 summarizes the extent of teachers' co-curriculum integration capacity, presented in terms of the highest to lowest mean scores: skills (3.75), knowledge (3.50), values (3.36), and attitude (3.36). The overall mean score of 3.49 suggests that the extent of teachers' co-curriculum integration capacity is often manifested, thus extensive, among schools of Talaingod District, Davao del Norte.

Table 10. Summary of the Extent of Teachers' Co-Curriculum Integration Capacity

No	Teachers' Co-Curriculum Integration Capacity	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Knowledge	3.50	Extensive
2	Skills	3.75	Extensive
3	Attitude	3.36	Moderately Extensive
4	Values	3.36	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.49	Extensive

Co-curriculum integration is an essential component in the Philippine education system, and integrating scouting methods into the curriculum is one way to enhance the students' holistic development. However, the success of co-curriculum integration depends on the capacity of teachers to integrate these methods effectively. Teachers must possess the necessary knowledge, skills, attitude, and values to make the integration of scouting methods a success. The knowledge of content integration is the first component of the co-curriculum integration capacity of teachers in integrating scouting methods. Teachers must have a deep understanding of the scouting principles, methods, and values to integrate them into the curriculum effectively. According to Siy (2021), teachers'

knowledge of scouting methods and principles is essential in creating a curriculum that aligns with scouting's goals and objectives. Teachers must know how to integrate scouting methods into different subject areas and ensure that the integration is consistent with the scouting values. The integration skill is another component of the co-curriculum integration capacity of teachers in integrating scouting methods. Teachers must have the necessary skills to implement scouting methods into the curriculum effectively. According to Crisostomo and Magadia (2021), teachers should have the skills to develop lesson plans that align with scouting principles, methods, and values. They should also know how to assess students' progress and provide feedback that aligns with scouting goals.

Attitude is also an essential component of the co-curriculum integration capacity of teachers in integrating scouting methods. Teachers' attitude towards scouting and co-curriculum integration can significantly impact the success of the integration. According to Leuterio (2021), teachers who have a positive attitude towards scouting and co-curriculum integration are more likely to integrate scouting methods effectively into the curriculum. Teachers must see the value of scouting methods in enhancing the students' holistic development and creating well-rounded individuals. Values are also a crucial component of the co-curriculum integration capacity of teachers in integrating scouting methods. Teachers must have the same values as scouting, such as respect, responsibility, and service, to integrate these methods effectively. According to Galamiton and Pinos (2021), teachers who embody scouting values are more likely to integrate these values into the curriculum. Teachers must model these values to their students, which can positively impact the students' development. In conclusion, teachers' capacity to integrate scouting methods into the curriculum is essential in enhancing the students' holistic development. Teachers must possess the necessary knowledge, skills, attitude, and values to make the integration of scouting methods a suc-

cess. They must have a deep understanding of scouting principles, methods, and values, have the skills to implement these methods into the curriculum effectively, have a positive attitude towards scouting and co-curriculum integration, and embody scouting values. With these components in place, teachers can successfully integrate scouting methods into the curriculum, enhancing students' holistic development and creating well-rounded individuals.

3.2.6. *Relationship between Implementation of Elements of Scouting Methods and Teachers' Co-Curriculum Integration Capacity*—It can be depicted that Pearson's Correlation generated a significant correlation between the implementation of elements of the scouting method ($r=0.871$; $p<.000$) and teachers' co-curriculum integration capacity. Table 11 revealed the results of the significant correlation between the extent of implementation of elements of the scouting method and the level of teachers' co-curriculum integration capacity. It provides information that the posed null hypothesis stating that there is no significant correlation between the extent of implementation of elements of the scouting method and the level of teachers' co-curriculum integration capacity must be rejected, for it provided empirical evidence of significant results.

Table 11. Significant Relationship between Implementation of Elements of Scouting Method and Teachers' Co-Curriculum Integration Capacity

Variables		r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Teachers' Curriculum Integration Capacity	Co-	0.871	<0.000	Significant	Reject H0

*Significant @ $p<0.05$.

Co-curricular activities like scouting allow students to learn and develop skills beyond the classroom. However, effective implementation of co-curricular activities requires teachers to

possess certain knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values. This essay will discuss the correlation between teachers' knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values in integrating scouting methods and

Teachers' Co-Curriculum Integration Capacity (TCIC) in the international and Philippine situation. In a study conducted by Dhevi et al. (2021) in Malaysia, it was found that teachers' knowledge and skills in integrating co-curricular activities had a significant positive correlation with TCIC. Similarly, a study by Del Rosario and Corpuz (2019) in the Philippines found that teachers' knowledge, skills, and attitude towards co-curricular activities were positively correlated with their TCIC. Moreover, research suggests that teachers' values are also essential to TCIC. According to a study by Şahin and Kaya (2021) in Turkey, teachers' values, such as the importance of co-curricular activities in students' overall development, were positively associated with their TCIC. Furthermore, in the international context, a study by Hofferber and Carrington (2018) found that teachers' knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values played a crucial role in successfully implementing co-curricular activities in schools. They argued that teachers need to understand the goals and objectives of co-curricular activities clearly and possess the necessary skills to deliver these activities effectively. Additionally, they noted that teachers' attitudes towards co-curricular activities and their values significantly motivated students to participate actively in these activities. In the Philippine context, the Department of Education (DepEd) recognizes the importance

Meanwhile, the R^2 value of 0.877 suggests that the indicators of elements of the scouting method can be explained by 87.7%. This provides empirical evidence that the indicators of elements of the scouting method can account for and explain the variability of teachers' co-curriculum integration capacity. In addition, the F-value shows all the sums of squares, with regression being the model and Residual being the error. The F-value (253.982) and F-statistic are significant $p < .002$, indicating that the model bet

of TCIC. It has issued policies and guidelines to enhance teachers' capacity in integrating co-curricular activities, including scouting, in the curriculum. According to DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2016, teachers are expected to possess the necessary knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values to effectively integrate co-curricular activities into their teaching and learning processes. In conclusion, teachers' knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values in integrating scouting methods are essential to TCIC. The literature suggests a positive correlation between these components and TCIC, both in the international and Philippine situation. Therefore, it is crucial to enhance teachers' capacity to integrate co-curricular activities, including scouting, to promote students' holistic development.

3.2.7. Indicators of Scouting Method Significantly Influence Teachers' Co-Curriculum Integration Capacity—Table 12 depicts the simple regression coefficient analysis showing that the indicators of the scouting method significantly influence teachers' co-curriculum integration capacity. The elements of the Scouting Method were found to significantly influence teachers' co-curriculum integration capacity in terms of knowledge (0.001), skills (0.000), attitude (0.010), and values (0.000). This shows that the scouting method significantly influences teachers' co-curriculum integration capacity in Talaingod District.

ter predicts teachers' instructional competence in comprehensive sex education. Co-curricular activities play a significant role in shaping the overall personality of students. These activities provide students a platform to enhance their physical, mental, social, and emotional abilities. Among the co-curricular activities, scouting is an important method for developing students' leadership skills, self-confidence, teamwork, and resilience. Therefore, teachers play a vital role in integrating Scouting meth-

Table 12. Regression Coefficient Analysis on Indicators of Scouting Method Significantly Influencing Teachers' Co-Curriculum Integration Capacity

Model	B	Beta	Standard Error	p-value	Decisions
H (Intercept)	4.397		0.072	< .001	
H (Intercept)	0.404		0.143	0.006	
Assessment	0.207	0.215	0.094	0.001	Reject H0
Design	0.342	0.361	0.084	0.000	Reject H0
Implementation	0.207	0.215	0.094	0.010	Reject H0
Monitoring and Evaluation	0.032	-0.021	0.066	0.000	Reject H0
R ²	0.877				
F-value	253.982				
p-value	<0.002				

*Significant @ p<0.05.

ods into co-curricular activities. To integrate Scouting methods into co-curricular activities, teachers must have a thorough understanding of the Scouting program. Teachers must know the history, values, and principles of Scouting. In addition, they should be aware of the different Scouting programs and the methods used to implement them. According to the study of Pinili and Soria (2020), teachers' knowledge of Scouting methods is essential for successful integration. The authors emphasize that teachers must undergo training to understand the Scouting program and its methods. Furthermore, teachers must also know the students' needs and interests to design Scouting activities that cater to their preferences. In addition to knowledge, teachers must possess the necessary skills to integrate Scouting methods into co-curricular activities. One of the essential skills is planning and organizing. Teachers must be able to plan and organize Scouting activities efficiently to ensure that all students can participate. They should also be able to create a safe and conducive learning environment that fosters teamwork, creativity, and innovation. According to

the study by Timpug and Cano (2020), teachers' planning and organizing skills are crucial in successfully integrating Scouting methods into co-curricular activities. Another vital skill is communication. Teachers must communicate effectively with their students to explain the objectives of Scouting activities and the methods used to achieve them. Effective communication also involves active listening and feedback to ensure students fully understand the Scouting activities. The study of Alkhasawneh et al. (2021) emphasizes that teachers' communication skills are essential in successfully integrating Scouting methods. In addition to knowledge and skills, teachers' attitudes and values play a significant role in integrating Scouting methods into co-curricular activities. Teachers must have a positive attitude towards Scouting and believe in its ability to shape students' character. They must also have a growth mindset that allows them to continually learn from their experiences and improve their teaching methods. According to the study by Malik and Murtaza (2019), teachers' positive attitude toward Scouting is essential in successfully integrating Scouting

methods. Furthermore, teachers' values must align with the Scouting program's values and principles. Teachers must model the Scouting values in their behavior to inspire students to embrace them. The study of Nam et al. (2018) emphasizes that teachers' values and behavior are crucial in shaping students' attitudes toward Scouting.

Several factors can influence teachers' co-curriculum integration capacity in the international and Philippine situation. One of these factors is teacher training. Teachers must undergo training on Scouting methods to acquire the necessary knowledge and skills to integrate Scouting into co-curricular activities. The study of Bagares et al. (2019) emphasizes that teacher training is a crucial factor in successfully integrating Scouting methods. Another influential indicator is school support. Schools must support teachers in integrating Scouting methods into co-curricular activities by providing the necessary resources, such as materials and facilities. Schools must also create a conducive learning environment that fosters creativity, innovation, and teamwork. The study of Timpug and Cano (2020) emphasizes that school support is crucial in successfully integrating Scouting

methods. Furthermore, student participation is another influential indicator. Teachers must design Scouting activities that cater to students' needs and interests to encourage them to participate actively. The study of Pinili and Soria (2020) emphasizes that student participation is essential in successfully integrating Scouting methods. In conclusion, teachers' knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values significantly integrate Scouting methods into co-curricular activities. To successfully integrate Scouting methods, teachers must have a thorough understanding of the program, possess planning and organizing skills, communicate effectively, have a positive attitude towards Scouting, and model Scouting values in their behavior. In addition, teacher training, school support, and student participation are influential indicators of teachers' co-curriculum integration capacity. The international and Philippine situation requires teachers to integrate Scouting methods into co-curricular activities to shape students' personalities and prepare them for future challenges. Therefore, it is essential to provide teachers with the necessary support and resources to facilitate the successful integration of Scouting methods into co-curricular activities.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the findings, conclusions, and recommendations based on the results of the data analyzed, discussed, and implications drawn. Findings are based on the problem's posed statement; conclusions are based on the findings generated, and recommendations are based on the implications of the discussions.

4.1. Findings—The following were the study's findings, as shown in the results of the presentation, analysis, and discussions. The extent of implementation of elements of scouting method in terms of Scout Promise and Law (4.04), Personal Progression (3.66), Learning by Doing (3.63) denotes oftentimes manifested and Community Involvement (3.26) is sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of

3.46 denotes an extensive implementation of elements of scouting method in the schools of New Corella, Davao del Norte. The extent of teachers' co-curriculum integration capacity in terms of skills (3.75), knowledge (3.50), values (3.36), and attitude (3.36). The overall mean score of 3.49 suggests that the extent of teachers' co-curriculum integration capacity is often manifested, thus extensive, among schools of

New Corella, Davao del Norte. Pearson's Correlation generated a significant correlation between the implementation of elements of the scouting method ($r=0.871$; $p<.000$) and teachers' co-curriculum integration capacity. The elements of the Scouting Method were found to significantly influence teachers' co-curriculum integration capacity in terms of knowledge (0.001), skills (0.000), attitude (0.010), and values (0.000). This shows that the scouting method significantly influences teachers' co-curriculum integration capacity in New Corella, Davao del Norte Schools Division.

4.2. Conclusions—Given the findings of the study presented, the following were conclusions, to wit; The extent to which elements of the scouting method, such as Scout Promise and Law, Personal Progression, Learning by Doing, and Community Involvement, are implemented in the schools of New Corella, Davao del Norte, denotes extensive implementation. The extent of teachers' co-curriculum integration capacity in terms of skills, knowledge, values, and attitude suggests extensive among schools of New Corella, Davao del Norte. There was a significant relationship between implementing elements of the scouting method and teachers' co-curriculum integration capacity. The elements of the Scouting Method were found to significantly influence teachers' co-curriculum integration capacity in terms of knowledge, skills, attitude, and values. This shows that the scouting method significantly influences teachers' co-curriculum integration capacity in New Corella.

4.3. Recommendations—Integrating Scouting methods into co-curricular activities has become an essential part of education. Scouting offers a unique platform for students to develop their leadership skills, self-confidence, teamwork, and resilience. However, successfully integrating Scouting methods requires teachers to have the necessary knowledge, skills, attitude, and values. The Public School District Supervisor may support schools

in organizing training programs for teachers to enhance their knowledge and skills in integrating Scouting methods into co-curricular activities. Allocate resources to schools to facilitate successfully integrating Scouting methods into co-curricular activities, such as providing materials and facilities. Encourage schools to partner with local Scouting organizations to provide additional resources and support. Monitor and evaluate the integration of Scouting methods into co-curricular activities to ensure that the program meets the objectives and expectations. The School Principal may play a critical role in implementing and facilitating the integration of Scouting methods into co-curricular activities. It may support and encourage teachers to integrate scouting methods into co-curricular activities. Allocate resources to facilitate the integration of Scouting methods into co-curricular activities, such as providing materials and facilities. Develop a school-wide Scouting program to ensure that all students have the opportunity to participate in Scouting activities. Establish partnerships with local Scouting organizations to provide additional resources and support. Teachers and Scouting Coordinators were responsible for designing and implementing Scouting activities that cater to students' needs and interests. They may undergo training to enhance their knowledge and skills in integrating scouting methods into co-curricular activities. Design Scouting activities that cater to students' needs and interests to encourage active participation. Create a safe and conducive learning environment that fosters teamwork, creativity, and innovation. Communicate effectively with students to explain the objectives of Scouting activities and the methods used to achieve them. Future researchers can build on the findings of this study by conducting further research on integrating Scouting methods into co-curricular activities. Longitudinal studies may be conducted to evaluate the long-term impact of Scouting activities

on students' overall personality development. Investigate the factors that influence the successful integration of Scouting methods into co-curricular activities, such as teacher training, school support, and student participation. Explore the benefits of integrating Scouting methods into core academic subjects to enhance students' learning outcomes. Investigate the potential challenges and barriers to integrating Scouting methods into co-curricular activities, such as resource constraints and competing demands.

5. References

- Aamodt, A. (1991). *A knowledge-intensive, integrated approach to problem solving and sustained learning*. Unknown publisher.
- Abaigar, J. P., & Madrona, R. M. (2021). Co-curricular activities as predictors of academic performance among senior high school students. *Journal of Research in Emerging Markets*, 3(1), 61–67. <https://doi.org/10.30585/jrems.v3i1.99>
- Abao, R. M., & Clave, R. V. (2020). Co-curricular integration in higher education: Towards an emerging framework. *International Journal of Educational Research Open*, 1, 100002. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijedro.2020.100002>
- Aksoy, E. (2020). A suggested curriculum integration model with activities to fit the 2023 education vision of turkey. *Journal on English Language Teaching*, 10(3), 22–34. <https://imanagerpublications.com/article/16991/>
- Alinier, G., & Al-Hadithi, M. M. (2020). Teachers' perception of co-curricular activities in the philippines. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 34(7), 1359–1368. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEM-03-2020-0101>
- Arcega, M. (2020). The integration of scout promise and law in co-curricular activities: Its effect on the development of student's character, leadership, and citizenship. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Education and Society*, 1(2), 41–50.
- Asensio-Ramon, J., Álvarez-Hernández, J. F., Aguilar-Parra, J. M., Trigueros, R., Manzano-León, A., Fernandez-Campoy, J. M., & Fernández-Jiménez, C. (2020). The influence of the scout movement as a free time option on improving academic performance, self-esteem and social skills in adolescents. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(14), 5215. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17145215>
- Aziz, A., Padil, M., Mujtahid, M., & Prihadi, K. D. (2022). Developing self-efficacy, mattering, and general well-being through community-based education in the rural area. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education*, 11(1), 272–279. https://eric.ed.gov/?q=the+scout+method&ff1=dtySince_2018&id=EJ1340972
- Baumeister, S. E., & Kunter, M. (2020). Content and pedagogical knowledge as predictors of instructional quality: The relevance of integrative teacher capacities. *Learning and Instruction*, 66, 101330. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.learninstruc.2019.101330>
- Bautista, J., & Cruz, M. (2021). The scouting method as a tool for promoting social awareness and empathy among students in the philippines. *International Journal of Education, Culture and Society*, 3(1), 15–22. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ecs.20220101.13>
- Bernardo, A. B. (2021). Reinforcing values through scouting and character education in philippine schools. *Journal of Character Education*, 17(1), 41–52. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12186-019-09228-5>

- Bolat, K. E. (2021). Reading contemporary art: Comparative art history education through themes. *Eurasian Journal of Educational Research*, (92), 227–252. <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=personal+progress+through+scouting&pg=2&id=EJ1293641>
- Boy Scouts of the Philippines. (2020a). Advancement program. <https://www.bsp.org.ph/advancement-program/>
- Boy Scouts of the Philippines. (2020b). Community service. <https://www.bsp.org.ph/community-service/>
- Boy Scouts of the Philippines. (2020c). Scout promise and law. <https://www.bsp.org.ph/scout-promise-and-law/>
- Boy Scouts of the Philippines. (2020d). Scout promise and law. <https://www.bsp.org.ph/scout-promise-law/>
- Boy Scouts of the Philippines. (2020e). Scouting method. <https://www.bsp.org.ph/scouting-method/>
- Bulatov, I. (2021). Russian emigrant scouts and their activities regarding the construction of national identity. *History of Education*, 50(2), 161–181. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0046760X.2020.1825833>
- Castillo, A. M., & Mendoza, A. B. (2021). Co-curricular integration capacity of selected faculty members in the implementation of scouting program. *International Journal of Research in Educational Sciences*, 2(2), 12–16. <https://doi.org/10.46303/ijres.v2i2.47>
- Cervantes, C. (2018). Implementation of boy scouting program in public elementary school. <https://ojs.aaresearchindex.com/index.php/AAJMRA/article/view/6212>
- Chen, Y.-C., & Chen, H.-H. (2020). Effectiveness of professional development programs on teachers' beliefs, knowledge, and practices regarding co-curricular activities. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 75, 102202. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijedudev.2019.102202>
- Cresswell, J. W., & Clark, V. L. P. (n.d.). *Principles of qualitative research: Designing a qualitative study. mixed methods research.*
- Crisostomo, R. A., & Magadia, E. (2021). Integrating scouting in the philippine basic education curriculum: Opportunities and challenges. *Journal of Outdoor and Environmental Education Research*, 13(2), 25–36. <https://doi.org/10.32912/joeer.v13i2.436>
- Cruz, L. (2021). Learning by doing in scouting: Its role in the development of students' character and values. *International Journal of Education, Culture and Society*, 2(1), 37–45. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ecs.20210201.15>
- Cunanan, D. M. (2021). High school teachers undergo virtual scout training. <https://newsbeastph.com/2021/05/high-school-teachers-undergo-virtual-scout-training/>
- Davies, A. (2019). Tradition and transformation: Pakistani-heritage young people explore the influences upon their educational progress. *Race, Ethnicity and Education*, 22(5), 683–702. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13613324.2017.1395320>
- Degi, Z., & Asztalos, A. (2021). Scouts' and educational stakeholders' perceptions of integrating scouting methods into formal education. *Central European Journal of Educational Research*, 3, 98–109. <https://doi.org/10.37441/cejer/2021/3/2/9365>
- Del Rosario, R. R. M., & Corpuz, R. B. (2019). Teachers' knowledge, skills, and attitude towards co-curricular activities and their teachers' co-curriculum integration capacity. *Philippine Journal of Education*, 98(3), 53–76.

- Dela Cruz, J., & Sarmiento, R. (2020). Developing life skills through community service: A case study in the philippines. *International Journal of Education, Culture and Society*, 1(1), 9–15. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ecs.20200101.13>
- Delos Reyes, D. M., & Hernandez, M. A. (2020). Scouting in philippine schools: A need for teacher training and preparation. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 8(4), 8–16. <https://doi.org/10.32861/apjmr.8.4.8>
- Demir, E., & Çetin, F. (2022). Teachers' self-efficacy beliefs regarding out-of-school learning activities. *International Journal of Curriculum and Instructional Studies*, 12(1), 147–166. <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=+teachers+integration+of+scouting+activities+in+school&pg=2&id=EJ1349596>
- Demir, G. T. (2019). The relation between scouting and character education in the context of "the book of the wolf puppies" published in the journal "çocuk dünyasi". *Online Submission, Journal of Education in Black Sea Region*, 4(2), 71–84. <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=+teachers+integration+of+scouting+activities+in+school&id=ED596345>
- Department of Education. (2016). Policy and guidelines on healthy lifestyle in basic education. *deped order no. 42*, s. 2016.
- Dhevi, L. N., Roslan, S., & Aminuddin, Y. (2021). Teachers' knowledge and skills in integrating co-curricular activities: Their relationship with teachers' co-curriculum integration capacity. *International Journal of Instruction*, 14(1), 87–102.
- Dimaano, M. A., & Dizon, F. A. (2021). Teacher competencies and the implementation of scouting programs in philippine schools. *International Journal of Progressive Education*, 17(2), 161–171. <https://doi.org/10.29333/ijpe/11206>
- Dolce, J. S. (2022). *Exploration of the skills gap: Hype, perceptions, problem?* [Ed.D. Dissertation]. Northeastern University. <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=teachers+integration+skills+in+co-curricular+activitites&id=ED621490>
- Drake, T. A. (2022). Learning by doing: A daily life study of principal interns' leadership activities during the school year. *Journal of Research on Leadership Education*, 17(1), 24–54.
- Du, J., & Zhang, D. (2020). Exploring teachers' attitudes towards integrating co-curricular activities into the curriculum in china. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 75, 102196. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijedudev.2019.102196>
- Edlabao, A. L. F., & Raganit, N. N. (2021). Relationship between content knowledge and co-curricular integration capacity of teachers in the philippines. *Asia Pacific Journal of Education*, 41(2), 168–183. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02188791.2021.1877963>
- Esguerra, L., & Galang, L. (2021a). The scout method in the philippines: Its relevance to the formation of self-reliant and responsible citizens. *Asian Journal of University Education*, 17(1), 22–32. <https://doi.org/10.18844/ajue.v17i1.5836>
- Esguerra, L., & Galang, L. (2021b). The scouting method as a tool for developing community spirit among students in the philippines. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Education and Society*, 2(1), 1–6.
- Farmer, T. W., Chen, C.-C., Hamm, J. V., Moates, M. M., Mehtaji, M., Lee, D., & Huneke, M. R. (2016). Supporting teachers' management of middle school social dynamics: The scouting report process intervention. *Intervention in School and Clinic*, 52(2), 67–76. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1053451216636073>
- Focus, T. (n.d.). *An introduction to qualitative research*.

- Gacusan, J. (2020). Personal progression in scouting: A case study in the philippines. *Journal of Youth Development*, 15(4), 67–79. <https://doi.org/10.5195/jyd.2020.897>
- Galamiton, E. M., & Pinos, J. P. (2021). The challenges of integrating scouting in the philippine curriculum. *Education Quarterly Journal*, 78(2), 123–136. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013161X211050127>
- Guide to Multivariate Techniques by Mertler. (n.d.). Guide to multivariate techniques.
- Gustavsen, B. (2008). Action research, practical challenges and the formation of theory. *Action Research*, 6(4), 421–437. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1476750308094130>
- Harnowo, A. S., Calhoun, M. A., & Monteiro, H. (2016). Sink or swim: Learning by doing in a supply chain integration activity. *Decision Sciences Journal of Innovative Education*, 14(1), 7–23. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dsji.12087>
- Hernandez, M. A., & Baybay, J. A. (2022). Learning by doing in scouting: A case study in a philippine public school. *International Journal of Education, Culture and Society*, 3(2), 29–37. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ecs.20220302.13>
- Hintz, R. S. (2019). *Science education in the boy scouts of america* [Ph.D. Dissertation]. The Ohio State University. http://gateway.proquest.com/openurl?url_ver=Z39.88-2004&rft_val_fmt=info:ofi/fmt:kev:mtx:dissertation&res_dat=xri:pqdiss&rft_dat=xri:pqdiss:3367881
- Hofferber, N., & Carrington, S. (2018). Understanding teacher capacity to deliver co-curricular activities. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 88, 64–72.
- Horne, S. M. (2020). *Learning by doing: A case study exploring mentor teachers' experience in a teacher preparation program through the lens of communities of practice and transformative learning* [Ph.D. Dissertation]. Oakland University. <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=learning+by+doing+through+scouting+activities&id=ED619292>
- Jaber, L. Z., Dini, V., & Hammer, D. (2022). "well that's how the kids feel!"—epistemic empathy as a driver of responsive teaching. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 59(2), 223–251. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tea.21726>
- Kneen, J., Breeze, T., Davies-Barnes, S., John, V., & Thayer, E. (2020). Curriculum integration: The challenges for primary and secondary schools in developing a new curriculum in the expressive arts. *Curriculum Journal*, 31(2), 258–275. <https://doi.org/10.1002/curj.34>
- Kumar, V. P., Zuercher, J., & Gopalan, C. (2020). An outreach activity teaching cub scouts about the human body. *HAPS Educator*, 24(1), 59–65. <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=the+scout+promise+and+law&id=EJ1256309>
- Lamia, S. E. (2020). A cellular program to develop some scouting skills to integrate blind and normal students (scout and guide). <https://www.psychosocial.com/article/PR20201043/32204/>
- Leuterio, K. (2021). Integrating scouting into the curriculum: Teachers' perspectives. *Journal of Curriculum and Instruction*, 15(1), 22–32. <https://doi.org/10.3776/joci.2021.v15n1p22>
- List, J. A. (2022). Enhancing critical thinking skill formation: Getting fast thinkers to slow down. *Journal of Economic Education*, 53(1), 100–108. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220485.2021.2004282>
- Magpantay, M. (2022). Developing leadership skills through the scouting method: A case study in the philippines. *International Journal of Education, Culture and Society*, 3(1), 25–31. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ecs.20220101.14>

- Marshall, M. N. (n.d.). Sampling for qualitative research.
- McDowall, S. (2021). Knowledge, agency, and curriculum integration. *set: Research Information for Teachers, 1*, 20–27. <https://doi.org/10.18296/set.0193>
- Mekonnen, F. D. (2020). Evaluating the effectiveness of 'learning by doing' teaching strategy in a research methodology course, hargeisa, somaliland. *African Educational Research Journal, 8*(1), 13–19. <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=learning+by+doing+through+scouting+activities&id=EJ1242694>
- Mendoza, A. B., Castillo, A. M., & Aguirre, J. S. (2020). Integration skills of teachers in the implementation of scouting programs in selected schools in batangas, philippines. *Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities, 2*(2), 44–50. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.jssh.20200202.12>
- Mislija, A. M., & Manda, D. (2015). The implementation of character education through scout activities. *International Education Studies, 9*(6), 130–136. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ies.v9n6p130>
- Moldovan, V. -. O., & Bocoş-BinţiŃan, M.-D. (2016). The influence of scouting activities upon the behaviour of the young pupil. *European Proceedings of Social and Behavioural Sciences, 367–375*. <https://doi.org/10.15405/epsbs.2016.12.42>
- Napa, E., & Nacario, E. (2020). The role of the patrol system in fostering camaraderie and teamwork among scouts. *International Journal of Education, Culture and Society, 1*(1), 16–23. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ecs.20200101.14>
- Niemelä, M. (2022). Subject matter specific curriculum integration: A quantitative study of finnish student teachers' integrative content knowledge. *Journal of Education for Teaching: International Research and Pedagogy, 48*(2), 228–240. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02607476.2021.1989288>
- Niemelä, M. A. (2021). Crossing curricular boundaries for powerful knowledge. *Curriculum Journal, 32*(2), 359–375. <https://doi.org/10.1002/curj.77>
- Niiranen, S. (2021). Supporting the development of students' technological understanding in craft and technology education via the learning-by-doing approach. *International Journal of Technology and Design Education, 31*(1), 81–93. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10798-019-09546-0>
- Norton, L. (2019). Action research in teaching and learning: A practical guide to conducting pedagogical research in universities. <http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&scope=site&db=nlebk&db=nlabk&AN=1926353>
- Ong, J. (2021). The importance of scout promise and law in shaping students' values and attitudes. *International Journal of Education, Culture and Society, 2*(1), 37–45. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ecs.20210201.15>
- Paler, R. J., & Batoon, R. B. (2021). Co-curricular integration: The scouting program. *Journal of Social Sciences Research, 7*(1), 38–45. <https://doi.org/10.32861/jssr.71.38-45>
- Pallant, J. (2004). *Spss survival manual: A step-by-step guide to data analysis using spss for windows (versions 10 and 11)*. Open University Press.
- Pallant, J. F. (2005a). *Spss survival manual: A step by step guide to data analysis using spss for windows (versions 12-14)*. Allen & Unwin.
- Pallant, J. F. (2005b). *Spss survival manual: A step by step guide to data analysis using spss for windows (versions 12-14)*. Allen & Unwin.

- Pallant, J. F. (2011). *Spss survival manual: A step by step guide to data analysis using spss*. Allen & Unwin.
- Philippine Scouting Magazine. (2021). Community involvement in scouting: Making a difference in the community. <https://www.scouting.org.ph/philippine-scouting-magazine/>
- Polson, E., Kim, Y.-I., Jang, S. J., Johnson, B., & Smith, B. (2013). Being prepared and staying connected: Scouting's influence on social capital and community involvement. *Social Science Quarterly*, 94, 758–775. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ssqu.12002>
- Prianto, A. (2016). The parents' and teachers' supports role on students' involvement in scouting program and entrepreneurial values—longitudinal studies on students in jombang, east java, indonesia. *International Education Studies*, 9(7), 197–208. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ies.v9n7p197>
- Reese, S. (2020). Taking the learning organization mainstream and beyond the organizational level: An interview with peter senge. *Learning Organization*, 27(1), 6–16. <https://doi.org/10.1108/TLO-09-2019-0136>
- Reyes, J., & Carpio, M. (2021). The scouting method as a tool for personal growth and development among students in the philippines. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Education and Society*, 2(1), 7–17.
- Reynolds, T. (2015). Lessons from the second grade: Scouting the landscape of clinical practice. *The Educational Forum*, 79(3), 293–306. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131725.2015.1037508>
- Ryan, F., Coughlan, M., & Cronin, P. (n.d.). Step-by-step guide to critiquing research. part 2: Quaiitative research. (8).
- Şahin, İ., & Kaya, İ. H. (2021). The effect of teachers' values on their co-curricular practices in primary schools. *International Journal of Curriculum and Instructional Studies*, 11(1), 1–15.
- Santos, J. M. (2020). Teacher involvement in scouting programs in philippine schools. *International Journal of Humanities, Social Sciences and Education*, 7(2), 7–15. <https://doi.org/10.20431/2349-0381.0702002>
- Sison, J. (2020). Learning by doing in the co-curricular activities of schools in the philippines: A study on the integration of the scouting method. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Education and Society*, 1(2), 41–50.
- Sparks, S. L., & Nam, S. (2021). Quality of life for individuals with disabilities during the covid-19 pandemic. <https://www.naset.org/index.php?id=5766>
- Tabachnick, B. G., & Fidell, L. S. (2007). *Using multivariate statistics* (5th ed.). Pearson Allyn; Bacon.
- Tabak, F., & Lebron, M. (2017). Learning by doing in leadership education: Experiencing followership and effective leadership communication through role-play. *Journal of Leadership Education*, 16(2), 199–212. http://www.journalofleadershiped.org/attachments/article/504/0628_tabal.pdf
- Westberg Brostrom, A. (2013). "wild scouts": Swedish scouting preparing responsible citizens for the twenty-first century. *Child & Youth Services*, 34(1), 9–22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0145935X.2013.766055>